

This paper is the Submitted Version of the following published contribution:

Kubičková, V., Micháľková, A., Gáll, J., Pinos-Navarrete, A., & Carballo-Cruz, E. (2025). The impact of cooperation on the innovation performance of spa tourism in European destinations. *International Journal of Spa and Wellness*, 8(3), 619-636.

The Impact of Cooperation on The Innovation Performance of Spa Tourism in European Destinations

Viera Kubičková¹, Anna Micháľková¹, Jozef Gáll¹, Aida Pinos-Navarrete², Edianny Carballo-Cruz³

1 Department of Tourism, Bratislava University of Economics and Business, Bratislava, Slovakia

2 Geografia Humana Department, University of Granada, Granada, Spain

3 Department of Organizational Management and Tourism, University of Ciego de Ávila, Ciego de Ávila, Cuba

Abstract

The article focuses on examining the relationships between various forms of cooperation among spa enterprises and their different areas of innovation performance, as well as their connections to different types of innovations. The study is based on available literature and expert surveys conducted in the field of spa tourism in Slovakia and Spain – countries with distinct spa financing systems. The cooperation of spa enterprises has a differentiated impact on their innovation performance, with a high degree of dispersion in correlation coefficients when analyzing individual variables. However, the examined relationships confirm the assertions about the positive link between cooperation and innovation, as stated in the relevant literature. This holds true despite the fact that most of the examined links were not found to be strong. The higher observed relationships between cooperation and innovation performance, as well as stronger connections between specific forms of partnerships in Spain, may imply a slightly higher level of innovation ecosystems in that country, along with greater pressure for innovation and utilization of collaborative potential. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that cooperation is an integral part of the innovation ecosystem and should be considered when designing innovation policies at both the national and regional levels.

Keywords: Cooperation, Spa Tourism, Innovation, Innovation Performance, Slovakia, Spain

Classification codes O39, L83, I13, Z32

1 Introduction

The issue of the relationship between business partnership ties and their innovation performance has been explored in several studies (Prokop et al., 2021; Wang & Hu, 2020; Audretsch et al., 2023; Xu et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2024; Cantabene & Grassi, 2024). This relationship is present both in theory developed within the contexts of manufacturing and services. The significant engagement in the role of cooperation in innovation performance is understandable in light of the need

for resource sharing and the effective generation and implementation of innovations. Business cooperation with research authorities can be considered a mediating variable in their innovation activities (Prokop et al., 2021; Tseng et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2024; Radicic & Alkaraan, 2024), with firms' technological advancement being a prerequisite for conducting cooperative research activities (Wu et al., 2020). The diversity of knowledge that cooperation brings enhances companies' innovation performance (Santoro et al., 2020). On the other hand, optimizing the number of partners and ties is an essential condition for achieving positive effects of cooperation on firms' innovation performance (Temel et al., 2023; Ismail et al., 2024).

The way and intensity of knowledge sharing within tourism networks impact the innovativeness of tourism businesses (McLeod et al., 2024; Valderrama & Polanco, 2024; Pikkemaat & Weiermair, 2007; Wilke et al., 2019; Wu, 2020). Ilic et al. (2023) examined the impact of regional tourism cooperation on the economic performance of businesses, identifying it as a crucial factor in business success. In the context of medical tourism, the influence of cooperation on the sector's innovation performance has been studied to a lesser extent. The quality of cooperation is reflected in the satisfaction of medical tourism clients (Perkumienė et al., 2019). Effective organizational partnerships in the medical tourism sector should be supported by state intervention (Banevicius & Narkiene, 2023), public-private partnerships (Semenova et al., 2020), and cluster networking support (Oborin et al., 2019).

Focusing on spa tourism reveals that the topic of the influence of cooperation on innovation performance represents a relatively underexplored area. The spa industry's implementation of innovations has been addressed in the works of several authors (Nagy, 2014; Szymanska & Lech, 2017; Trip et al., 2023; Rodek et al., 2020; Szromek & Polok, 2022). De Figueiredo et al. (2021) identify differences in the quantity, diversity, and types of relationships established between public and private stakeholders in the wellness and spa tourism sector. Emphasizing the quality of relationships within spa tourism cooperation is crucial, especially given the complex nature of the spa tourism product and the business model of spa enterprises (Szymańska et al., 2016; Barros & Sousa, 2022; Szromek & Polok, 2022). The core of the spa product is a medical service that is knowledge-intensive, with its quality depending on the implementation of the latest knowledge from various medical fields. This spa tourism product is further complemented by primary and supplementary tourism services.

It can be assumed that the sustainability of this complex mechanism's production depends on high-quality cooperation among partners from the business and public sectors, practice, and research. Therefore, the focus of this research is the cooperation of spa enterprises and its impact on their innovation performance, a still insufficiently explored area in the international context and within Slovakia. The study observes two spa tourism destinations with differing mechanisms for financing spa treatments: Slovakia and Spain.

The aim of the study is to evaluate the impact of spa enterprises' cooperation on their innovation performance, with an emphasis on different financing conditions in selected destinations.

1.2 Theoretical background and research framework

The sustainable development of economic activities depends on the advancement of knowledge and the implementation of innovations (Adams et al., 2016; Kiron et al., 2012). Generating these requires high-quality and abundant resources, making sharing and cooperation an effective mechanism. In the context of tourism, cooperation is defined as an efficient tool for development (Costa & Lima, 2018). This is related to the complexity of the product and the location-dependent conditions for its realization. In the case of spa tourism, the role of cooperation is even more pronounced due to the knowledge-intensive nature of the core product-medical services and the complex construction of the product, which combines medical and therapeutic services with tourism services (Blazevic, 2016).

The creation of collaborative networks involves multiple tourism sector stakeholders who work together to create value and offer tourists more comprehensive experiences (Hall & Williams, 2019). Cassens (Cassens et al., 2012) suggests addressing the existing knowledge gap regarding the effects of cooperation on innovations in spa tourism. There are several positive examples of cooperation in the context of innovations in spa tourism, such as the one described by Lebe (2013) in Central Europe, or a recent case of open innovation functioning presented by Szromek (2021). However, research findings on consumer behavior in spa tourism confirm that the demand for product innovations is not for entirely new products but rather for improvements to existing ones (Gil de Arriba, 2000; Gössling et al., 2012), which are assigned new practical values or enhanced qualitative parameters (Valeriani, Margarucci & Romano, 2018; Gómez et al., 2019). This modest demand for product innovations in spa tourism may indicate a weakened impact of cooperation on the implementation of product innovations and subsequently on a broader spectrum of related types of innovations and expected innovation-driven performance.

These findings provide opportunities for further verification of the relationship between cooperation and innovative performance in spa tourism. Accordingly, the null and alternative hypotheses were formulated as follows:

H₀: There is no relationship between the intensity of cooperation of spa companies and their innovative performance.

H₁: There is a relationship between the intensity of cooperation of spa companies and their innovative performance.

1.2.1 Tourism innovation and their adaptation in European spas

The success of a tourism product depends on its acceptance in the market. Innovation in customer experience focuses on satisfying tourists by creating unique and personalized experiences (Neuhofer, Buhalis & Ladkin, 2015). Identifying consumer needs, developing new products, procedures, and technologies to meet those needs, and adopting innovations are key challenges in tourism (Rodriguez Sanchez et al., 2020; Custódio Santos et al., 2020). However, in Mediterranean

regions, where the spa tourism consumer profile is relatively homogeneous, with a higher average age and traditional demands for product quality, the pressure for product innovation is limited (Pinos, Shaw & Martos, 2020). These consumer characteristics are also present in the context of Slovak spa tourism (National Center for Health Information, 2024). Nonetheless, the gradual sophistication of demand due to generational shifts in spa tourism consumers and the pressures of technological changes are creating a need for innovation.

Technological innovations, such as the use of digital technologies and artificial intelligence, represent a cross-cutting element across all types of innovation. The pressure for their implementation is a logical outcome of changes in demand, even within the relatively conservative spa tourism sector, as well as the availability of new techniques and technologies in diagnostic, therapeutic, and treatment procedures for spa clients. Technological innovation involves incorporating new tools and technological solutions to enhance the tourist experience and improve operational efficiency (Xiang et al., 2017). For instance, new and/or improved treatments for COVID-19 patients have been introduced at spas, including inhalation and hydroponic therapies with sulfurous mineral-medicinal waters and respiratory physiotherapy interventions against the coronavirus (Pinos & Shaw, 2021). Renovation of these establishments, diversification of supply and demand, reconceptualization of modern spas, and considering the territory as a space for endogenous development all illustrate the reactivation of thermal tourism through tourism innovation. However, there is a noticeable lack of studies on this subject, and innovation is often applied only sporadically for emerging improvements, highlighting a limitation that needs to be addressed.

In the area of organizational innovations, the practices of European spas primarily focus on organizational changes that enhance tourism operations to optimize customer experience, operational efficiency, and sustainability (Smith & Puczkó, 2014).

Marketing innovation involves novel strategies and methodologies to attract more tourists, extend their stay (average length of stay), and/or ensure their loyalty, often by leveraging new technologies and social media (Buhalis & Foerste, 2015). In spa tourism, notable actions are directed toward digital marketing or the use of ICTs to promote new online services at spas (Sánchez Rodríguez, 2022; Anaya-Aguilar et al., 2021). Traditionally, thermal tourism has been associated with an older audience. However, thermal destinations have begun to shift their offerings towards younger segments, with wellness programs adapted to different audiences, ranging from therapeutic tourism to family getaways or sports tourism, thus diversifying their products by applying innovation to the marketing strategies of thermal establishments.

The implementation of spa tourism products takes place in environments with rare natural resources that require strict protection mechanisms. Consequently, ecological practices and associated innovations are also central to the conditions for implementing spa tourism. Sustainability innovation relates to practices that reduce environmental impact, promote the responsible use of natural resources, and encourage social responsibility in tourism (Scott et al., 2019).

In this context, studies on thermal tourism emphasizing its health-related dimension have highlighted the importance of spas for the socioeconomic development of regions and as a sustainable tourism alternative. This is particularly relevant because a high percentage of these establishments are located in rural areas facing demographic challenges and population decline (Pinos, Shaw & Martos, 2020). This approach not only improves the reputation of the destination but also addresses the demands of increasingly environmentally conscious tourists. Beyond the economic and environmental dimensions, its contribution to social innovation should also be emphasized, as health systems subsidize spa stays for health purposes. These include treatments for healthcare workers, care and support for elderly individuals facing loneliness and/or health issues, and preventive and therapeutic stays for people over 65 (Moure et al., 2013; Pinos & Shaw, 2021). Thus, the pandemic has underscored the importance of innovating in thermal tourism businesses to remain competitive and demonstrate their commitment to social and health responsibility (Pinos & Shaw, 2021).

In some spa destinations, the product also includes rare cultural and historical landmarks. This creates opportunities for cooperation across diverse expertise domains and the application of knowledge from the cultural and creative industries to enhance the innovative performance of businesses (Santoro et al., 2020).

The complexity of the spa product value chain requires a multidisciplinary and multi-stakeholder system of partnerships, making open innovation an effective system for knowledge transfer in spa tourism (Mota et al., 2024). It provides opportunities for resource sharing, which is crucial for the implementation of innovations in tourism (Chen & Ling, 2024). Effective cooperation in spa enterprises, particularly its outcomes, necessitates the acquisition of cooperative skills by employees (Berzina, 2023).

Regarding the broad typological spectrum of innovations applicable to spa tourism, the following research question was posed:

RQ1: How intensively does the cooperation of spa enterprises in various interest partnerships influence the implementation of different types of innovations?

1.2.2 Spa tourism in Slovakia and Spain

Considering the natural potential of Slovak spas, their successful tradition, and high-quality medical and therapeutic competence, spa tourism can be identified as a key form of tourism in Slovakia. In the Slovak Republic, spa medical care is financed within the framework of the public health insurance system. Three categories of spa guests are identified.

Category "A": Clients whose expenses for spa treatment are financed by public health insurance.

Category "B": Clients whose medical procedures are financed by the health insurance system.

Category "C": Clients who finance spa treatment services from their own resources.

The classification of clients into categories A and B depends on their current health condition and the indication of the disease (Act No. 538/2005; Act No. 577/2004).

Currently, 31 spa companies and facilities provide spa care in Slovakia. In 2022, the bed capacity was 10,306, and 3,879 jobs were created and filled within spas (Statistical Office of The Slovak Republic, 2023). The number of patients treated in 2022 was 162,232 (National Center for Health Information, 2022). In 2023, 167,187 patients completed treatment in spa facilities, representing a 3.1 % increase compared to 2022. The majority of spa guests were domestic clientsself-payers, followed by domestic clients receiving financial support from health insurance. A smaller proportion (22,075) comprised clients from abroad, primarily from the Czech Republic (54 %), Israel (11.2 %), and Germany (9.6 %) (National Center for Health Information, 2024).

The total number of spa clients is further increased by visitors who come for wellness products, recreation, and other services not focused on medical spa treatment. The total number of accommodated guests in spa facilities in 2023 was 325,337, of which 84 % were domestic clients (Statistical Office of The Slovak Republic, 2024).

Currently, Spain has 113 active spas offering medical treatments and wellness services, with many located in regions such as Galicia, Catalonia, and Andalusia. According to the Instituto Geológico y Minero de España (IGME), the thermal waters in these spas have a unique composition, highly valued for respiratory, dermatological, and rheumatic therapies (IGME, 2022a). In 2022, Spanish spas recorded a total of 884,390 visitors, generating direct employment for 3,199 workers, with over 60 % of these positions being held by women (IGME, 2022b).

Thermal tourism in Spain has experienced significant growth in recent decades, supported by both the private sector and various public financing mechanisms. The public funding system for spas mainly centers around a single government support form: the social spa program of the Instituto de Mayores y Servicios Sociales (IMSERSO). Initiated in 1989, this program offers spa therapy services to seniors, facilitating access to subsidized spa treatments. Beneficiaries include retirees, disability pensioners, widows over 55, unemployment benefits recipients aged 60 or older, and Social Security beneficiaries aged 65 or more. The program's funding is annual and partially state-covered, with IMSERSO contributing 20-50 % of treatment costs. For 2024, 192,000 spots have been allocated across 90 spas, and funding is paid directly to the spas, with users covering the remainder. The price includes full-board accommodation, basic thermal treatments, leisure activities, and collective insurance (IMSERSO, n.d.). However, there is currently no national public health program that finances spa stays for younger adults needing therapeutic spa treatments. These groups must finance services themselves (Martín, 2014).

2 Material and methods

For this study, the database was obtained through a sociological survey method in the form of a questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed to cover four areas of innovative activity in spa enterprises: factors influencing innovation, intensity of cooperation, barriers to innovation, and innovation performance. Innovation

performance in the study is expressed as the scope of impacts generated by innovations driven by cooperation. The intensity of cooperation is measured by the extent of cooperation across its various forms. Each of these areas included specific factors that experts evaluated using a Likert scale ranging from 0 to 4, where each value indicated a different level of influence on the key areas mentioned above. This approach enabled the collection of data reflecting the perception and assessment of innovation processes and cooperation in spa enterprises in Slovakia and Spain.

The primary goal of the questionnaire survey was to analyze the importance of cooperation among spa enterprises in the context of developing innovative potential and innovation performance in spa tourism at the international level. The questionnaire was designed to provide a comprehensive view of the factors affecting innovation activities in this sector and to gather valuable insights from experts with experience in the field of spa innovation. Their task was to provide objective and informed opinions on current innovation trends and cooperation in this sector.

The questionnaires were distributed electronically between November 1, 2023, and March 31, 2024, with a total of 61 experts participating in the survey. To ensure the comparability and validity of the results, the questionnaires were made available in two language versions – one for Slovakia and the other for Spain. This approach ensured the consistency of the collected data across two distinct geographical and cultural contexts.

In the presented study, we examine and test the relationships between the intensity of cooperation among spa enterprises and their innovation performance using two datasets. The first dataset includes variables from two main areas: cooperation intensity and innovation performance, which is represented by 24 innovation performance factors in spas. In addition to the factors listed in Table 1 and Table 2, these include Increased Work Performance Quality, Availability of a Skilled Workforce, New Innovative Ideas, Employee Satisfaction and Loyalty, Participation in Research in the Fields of Medicine, Physiotherapy, and Balneology, Availability of the Latest Knowledge in Medicine, Physiotherapy, and Balneology, Increase in the Number of Clients, New Client Segments, Socially Responsible Image of the Service Provider, Higher Occupancy Rate, Cost Reduction, Increasing Labor Productivity a Higher Standard of Living for the Local Population. This dataset provides a comprehensive view of the relationship between various forms of cooperation and spa innovation performance in both countries. The second dataset focuses on variables related to cooperation intensity and selected variables from the area of spa innovation performance. Experts evaluated the intensity of cooperation's impact on a designated scale. Based on these evaluations, we identified the variables with the highest average values for each country (Slovakia and Spain). These variables are used for a more detailed analysis and interpretation of key relationships between cooperation and innovation performance. An overview of these variables is provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Structure of the Dataset for Analyzing the Links Between Cooperation Among Spa Enterprises and Innovation Performance

Group1	Intensity of Cooperation
_A	Cooperation or Membership in a Spa or Healthcare Cluster

	_B	Cooperation or Membership in a Tourism Cluster or Destination Management Organization
	_C	Cooperation with Universities
	_D	Cooperation or Membership in Specific Knowledge and Innovation Partnerships/Innovation Ecosystems/Innovation and Technology Clusters
	_E	Cooperation with High Schools
Slovakia		
Group2		Innovation Performance
	_A	Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty
	_B	Higher Revenues
	_C	Development of the Tourism Destination
	_D	Regional Specialization
	_E	Development of the Regional Economy
Spain		
Group2		
	_A	Greening of Products and Processes
	_B	New Marketing Processes
	_C	Availability of External Financial Resources for Business Development
	_D	Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty
	_E	Development of the Regional Economy

Source: Authors'own processing

To evaluate the impact of cooperation among spa enterprises within various stakeholder partnerships on the implementation of different types of innovations, we utilize a third dataset comprising two main groups of variables. The first Group1, labeled Intensity of Cooperation, includes variables representing the intensity of a spa enterprise's cooperation within various stakeholder partnerships. The second Group2, labeled Types of Innovations, consists of a set of variables reflecting different types of innovations. An overview of the dataset structure is provided in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Structure of the Dataset for Analyzing the Impact of Cooperation Among Spa Enterprises on the Implementation of Innovations

Group1		Intensity of Cooperation
	_A	Cooperation of the Spa Enterprise in Various Interest Partnerships
Group2		Types of Innovations
	_A	New Products and their Commercialization
	_B	New Methods and Processes in Service Production
	_C	Greening of Products and Processes
	_D	New Management Processes
	_E	New Marketing Processes

Source: Authors'own processing

For this study, the following hypotheses (H_0 and H_1) are established and tested separately for Slovakia and Spain. The evaluations are conducted at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, which represents the probability of rejecting the null hypothesis when it is true (Type I error):

H_0 : There is no relationship between the intensity of cooperation of spa companies and their innovative performance.

H_1 : There is a relationship between the intensity of cooperation of spa companies and their innovative performance.

The relationship between the intensity of cooperation among spa companies and their innovative performance is analyzed using Pearson's correlation coefficient (r), which quantifies the linear dependence between two variables. The correlation coefficient ranges from $[-1, 1]$, where values closer to 1 or -1 indicate a strong linear relationship (positive or negative) (Šoltés, 2019).

The results of the correlation analysis are visualized through a heatmap of the correlation matrix, enabling an intuitive display of the direction and strength of correlations between variables in each country. This method provides a clear representation of multiple correlations, while the interpretation of linear relationships is supplemented with a quantitative expression of the r coefficient (Šoltés, 2019).

To address our research question (RQ1: How intensively does the cooperation of spa enterprises in various interest partnerships influence the implementation of different types of innovations?), a paired t-test is used. This test compares the mean values between two dependent groups (paired samples). To ensure the reliability of the results, a 95 % confidence interval for the true difference between means is calculated, providing a range of values within which the true mean difference is highly likely to fall.

Statistical analyses are conducted using the R software package, which offers advanced tools for descriptive and inferential data analysis (R Core Team, 2024).

3 Results

The Relationship Between the Intensity of Cooperation Among Spa Companies and Their Innovation Performance in Slovakia

The relationship between the intensity of cooperation among spa companies (Group1) and their innovation performance (Group2) was analyzed using Pearson's correlation coefficient, which measures the strength and direction of the linear dependence between the examined variables. Hypothesis H_1 reflects the assumption that a relationship exists between the intensity of cooperation among spa enterprises and their innovation performance.

To test this hypothesis, a paired t-test was used to compare the means of these variables. The results showed that the mean difference between Group1 and Group2 values was -0.732 , indicating that, on average, the intensity of cooperation is lower than innovation performance. This difference is statistically significant ($t = -5.536$, $df = 45$, $p = 1.519 \times 10^{-6}$).

Since the p-value is significantly lower than the set significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), we reject the null hypothesis of no difference between the means. Instead, the results support the alternative hypothesis, asserting that a statistically significant relationship exists between the means.

The 95 % confidence interval for the mean difference ranges from -0.999 to -0.466. As the interval does not include zero and both bounds are negative, this confirms that the intensity of cooperation is systematically lower than innovation performance on average.

The Pearson correlation coefficient between Group1 and Group2 variables is $r = 0.312$, indicating **a weak to moderate positive correlation between the intensity of cooperation and innovation performance**. This suggests that higher cooperation intensity is somewhat associated with higher innovation performance, although the means reveal a difference in their levels.

These findings indicate a certain positive relationship between the intensity of cooperation and the innovation performance of spa companies in Slovakia. However, this relationship is weaker, and the average intensity of cooperation is systematically lower.

The relationships between individual variables within both Group1 (intensity of cooperation) and Group2 (innovation performance) were also examined. Variables from Group2 showing the highest cooperation intensity were selected for further analysis. The statistical test was conducted at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, with correlation coefficients and their p-values calculated for all intergroup combinations. The results are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Heatmap of Correlations Between Variables in Group1 (Intensity of Cooperation) and Group2 (Innovation Performance) for the Slovak Republic

Source: Authors' own processing

The strongest Pearson correlation coefficient (0.41) was observed between membership in a spa or healthcare cluster (Group1_A) and higher revenues (Group2_B), with a p-value lower than $\alpha = 0.05$, indicating statistical significance. This finding confirms that membership in spa or healthcare clusters can be a significant factor in improving customer satisfaction and loyalty. Similarly, a statistically significant relationship was also identified between cooperation or membership in specific knowledge and innovation partnerships/innovation ecosystems/innovation and technology clusters (Group1_D) and higher revenues (Group2_B), where the correlation coefficient reached 0.41, and the p-value was again below $\alpha = 0.05$. This relationship highlights the importance of technological and innovation partnerships for positive outcomes in client satisfaction and loyalty. On the other hand, most other correlations between Group1 and Group2 variables were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), suggesting that the intensity of cooperation may not generally correlate directly with all aspects of innovation performance.

Overall, the results partially support the proposed hypothesis. There is a statistically significant relationship between certain forms of cooperation among spa companies, such as membership in clusters (Group1_A) or engagement in innovation partnerships (Group1_D), and specific indicators of innovation performance, such as customer satisfaction and loyalty (Group2_A). However, these relationships are not universal, and other aspects of innovation performance, such as the development of tourism destinations (Group2_C) or regional economy (Group2_E), are less influenced by cooperation.

Based on these results, it can be concluded that the intensity of cooperation among spa companies has the potential to enhance their innovation performance. However, this relationship depends on the specific forms of cooperation and performance indicators.

Detailed insights into relationships between variables within and between groups are also valuable. Several moderate Pearson correlation coefficients were identified among variables in intensity of cooperation group (Group1), indicating notable interconnections. The highest coefficient (0.63) in Slovakia was found between cooperation with universities (Group1_C) and cooperation or membership in specific knowledge and innovation partnerships/innovation ecosystems/innovation and technology clusters (Group1_D). Similarly, a strong relationship was identified between cooperation with universities (Group1_C) and membership in tourism clusters or destination management organizations (Group1_B), with a coefficient of 0.58. This relationship suggests a synergistic effect between the academic sector and tourism development. Other notable but weaker relationships were observed between cooperation with high schools (Group1_E) and universities (Group1_C) (0.42), as well as between cooperation or membership in spa and healthcare clusters (Group1_A) and tourism clusters of destination management organizations (Group1_B) (0.52).

Within the innovation performance group (Group2), higher correlation coefficients were identified, indicating stronger interconnections among indicators in this group. The strongest relationship (0.79) was observed between development of the tourism destination (Group2_C) and development of the regional economy (Group2_E), emphasizing that tourism promotion significantly impacts broader economic

development. A notable relationship was also found between customer satisfaction and loyalty (Group2_A) and development of the tourism destination (Group2_C) (0.68), as well as between development of the regional economy (Group2_E) and higher revenues (Group2_B) (0.68). These results underline the importance of tourism development and economic initiatives for the overall success of innovations.

The Relationship Between Cooperation Intensity and Innovation Performance Among Spa Companies in Spain

Following the analysis of relationships between cooperation intensity and innovation performance among Slovak spa companies, a similar analysis was conducted for Spanish spa companies. This section evaluates the results for Spain, with correlation coefficients and p-values calculated for all combinations of variables across both groups.

To test the hypothesis that no relationship exists between the intensity of cooperation among spa companies (Group1) and their innovation performance (Group2), a paired t-test was used to compare the means of the two variables. The results showed that the mean difference between the variables was -0.757, and this difference was statistically significant ($t = -3.56$, $df = 17$, $p = 0.0024$).

Since the p-value is lower than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), the null hypothesis of no relationship between the means is rejected. Instead, the alternative hypothesis, which states that a statistically significant relationship exists between the means of cooperation intensity and innovation performance, is accepted.

The 95 % confidence interval for the mean difference ranges from -1.206 to -0.309. As this interval does not include zero and both bounds are negative, the results indicate that, on average, cooperation intensity is lower than innovation performance.

Additionally, the Pearson correlation coefficient between Group1 and Group2 variables was calculated at $r = 0.445$. This result indicates **a moderate positive correlation between cooperation intensity and innovation performance**. The correlation coefficient suggests that higher cooperation intensity is associated with higher innovation performance, although the paired t-test indicates a difference in the means of these variables.

These results are intriguing and suggest that there is a positive relationship between cooperation intensity and innovation performance. However, the difference in mean values implies that these indicators may not fully align.

Figure 2. Heatmap of Correlations Between Variables in Group1 (Intensity of Cooperation) and Group2 (Innovation Performance) for Spain

Source: Authors' own processing

As with Slovakia, the relationships between individual variables within each group, Group1 (intensity of cooperation) and Group2 (innovation performance), as well as between variables across both groups, were analyzed for Spain. Variables with the highest cooperation intensity were selected from the second group (Figure 2). Several strong Pearson correlation coefficients were identified, with the highest value (0.85) observed within Group1, specifically between cooperation or membership in spa or healthcare clusters (Group1_A) and cooperation or membership in specific knowledge and innovation partnerships (Group1_D). This strong relationship suggests synergistic effects between cooperative activities in healthcare clusters and advanced innovation partnerships. Similarly, a high coefficient (0.78) was recorded between cooperation with universities (Group1_C) and specific innovation partnerships (Group1_D). These results emphasize the key role of cooperation with educational institutions. Other notable relationships include the link between cooperation or membership in spa and healthcare clusters (Group1_A) and cooperation with universities (Group1_C), where the coefficient reached 0.76.

Within the innovation performance group (Group2), slightly weaker but still significant correlations were observed. The strongest relationship (0.60) was between the greening of products and processes (Group2_A) and customer satisfaction and loyalty (Group2_D). This relationship highlights the importance of eco-innovations for improving customer satisfaction, aligning with current trends in sustainable development. Other significant correlations include the connection between greening products and processes (Group2_A) and development of the regional economic development (Group2_E), with a coefficient of 0.52, and between regional economy

(Group2_E) and customer satisfaction and loyalty (Group2_D), with a coefficient of 0.49.

Intergroup relationships between Group1 and Group2 variables reveal that the intensity of spa companies' cooperation has a differentiated impact on innovation performance. The strongest positive relationship was observed between cooperation with universities (Group1_C) and development of the regional economy (Group2_E), where the correlation coefficient reached 0.56, indicating the importance of academic partnerships for economic development. Similarly, significant relationships were noted between cooperation in specific knowledge and innovation partnerships and access to external financial resources for business development (0.54). A weaker, yet present, relationship was also found between cooperation in tourism clusters or destination management organizations and regional economic development (0.41). Despite these positive findings, some relationships, such as between cooperation with high schools (Group1_E) and customer satisfaction and loyalty (Group2_D), showed very low correlation values (0.33) or even negative correlations, indicating varying impacts of different forms of cooperation.

The Relationship Between Spa Companies' Cooperation in Various Interest Partnerships and the Implementation of Different Types of Innovations

Further investigation focused on answering the research question posed in the theoretical background of this article, namely, RQ1: *How intensively does the cooperation of spa enterprises in various interest partnerships influence the implementation of different types of innovations?*

Figure 3 illustrates the relationships between the intensity of cooperation of the spa enterprise in various interest partnerships (Group1) and the implementation of different types of innovations (Group2). The correlation coefficients depicted on the heatmap provide insight into the strength of relationships between variables, allowing the identification of areas where cooperation has the most significant impact on the adoption of specific types of innovations.

Figure 3. Correlations Between Variables in Group1 (Cooperation of the Spa Enterprise in Various Interest Partnerships) and Group2 (Types of Innovations) for Slovakia and Spain

	Group2_A	Group2_B	Group2_C	Group2_D	Group2_E
SK Group1	0,40	0,45	0,25	0,51	0,40
ES Group1	0,60	0,50	0,39	0,43	0,07

Note: SK – Slovakia, ES – Spain
Source: Authors' own processing

In Slovakia, the most significant link between Group1 and the various types of innovations was observed in new management processes (Group2_D), where the correlation coefficient reached 0.51. This result indicates a moderately strong positive relationship, meaning that more intense cooperation among spa companies in interest partnerships tends to be associated with increased implementation of

innovative management processes. Similarly, the correlation coefficient for new methods and processes in service production (Group2_B) was 0.45. The intensity of cooperation here may play a key role in introducing more efficient or innovative production methods.

An important connection was also observed with new marketing processes (Group2_E), where the correlation coefficient was 0.40. This slightly positive relationship shows that cooperative activities support innovation in marketing, although to a lesser extent than in management processes. Another interesting finding is the relationship between cooperation and new products and their commercialization (Group2_A), where the correlation coefficient was 0.40. This result suggests a moderately positive link, with cooperation potentially contributing to more successful development and market introduction of new products.

For the greening of products and processes (Group2_C), the correlation coefficient was 0.25, indicating a weak positive relationship. While cooperation among spa companies in interest partnerships may be associated with eco-innovations, this link is relatively weak compared to other types of innovations.

Overall, the results in Slovakia suggest that the intensity of cooperation among spa companies in interest partnerships has a differentiated impact on various types of innovations. The strongest links are associated with the implementation of new management and production processes, while the greening of products and processes is the least influenced. These findings highlight the need for targeted cooperation, which could be tailored to support specific innovation goals.

The results of the analysis for Spain (Figure 3) also provide important insights into how cooperation among spa companies in interest partnerships is related to the implementation of different types of innovations. The most prominent relationship between Group1 and innovation was found in new products and their commercialization (Group2_A), where the correlation coefficient reached 0.60. This moderately strong positive relationship indicates that more intense cooperation is associated with more effective development and market introduction of new products. A similar, though slightly weaker, relationship was observed in new methods and processes in service production (Group2_B), where the correlation coefficient reached 0.50, still representing a moderately positive link. These results underscore the importance of cooperation in supporting process innovations.

For the greening of products and processes (Group2_C), a correlation coefficient of 0.39 was found, indicating a relatively weak positive connection. This result suggests that eco-innovations are less influenced by cooperative activities of spa companies. New management processes (Group2_D) showed a correlation coefficient of 0.43, again indicating a moderate positive relationship between cooperation and the implementation of innovations in this area. In contrast, the relationship between the intensity of cooperation and new marketing processes (Group2_E) was very weak, with a correlation coefficient of 0.07, indicating a practically negligible impact of cooperative activities on this type of innovation.

In Spain, the strongest links were observed in new products and production processes, while new marketing processes showed negligible connections.

4 Discussion and Conclusions

The results presented in the core of the article confirmed the formulated alternative hypothesis regarding a weak to moderate positive correlation between the intensity of cooperation and innovation performance in Slovakia and a moderate correlation in Spain. The research question concerning the types of innovations, within which similar-strength links were observed, has been answered.

Given the complex nature of the product and the visitor of spa resorts, as well as the natural connections to the location or region, alongside the very specific and diverse production resources in spa services, one might expect stronger links between cooperation in various forms of partnerships and innovation performance or types of innovations. However, the examined relationships confirm the accuracy of the literature on this issue, which identifies a connection between cooperation and innovation, even though many links were not proven to be strong in the study. The results not only allow for an assessment of the impact of cooperation on innovation and its effects in individual countries, but they also reveal some similarities and differences between them.

Of the five most significant effects of innovation resulting from spa enterprise cooperation based on the correlation coefficients, experts in both Slovakia and Spain agreed on two areas: client satisfaction and loyalty, and regional economic development. Experts from Slovakia, in contrast to those in Spain, do not consider the impact of cooperation on the greening of products and processes to be significant, while experts from Spain do not perceive the impact of cooperation on the development of tourism destinations as it is in Slovakia.

When examining the links between variables within both groups (Group1 and Group2), that is, between the intensity of cooperation and innovation performance (variables selected based on the highest impact of cooperation intensity), the results show a stronger connection in Spain compared to Slovakia. The correlation coefficient values in Spain (with a highest value of 0.56) are individually higher than in Slovakia (where the highest value is 0.41). Experts from Spain also tend to assess the connection between forms of cooperation and the effects of innovations as slightly stronger. However, it can be concluded that between Group1 and Group2, when examining the most significant effects of cooperation on innovation, there is a high degree of dispersion of correlation coefficients in both countries, with significantly higher dispersion in Spain (0.3604) compared to Slovakia (0.1079).

Cooperation between spa enterprises in various interest partnerships has very different effects on different areas of innovation performance. This is clearly demonstrated by the in-depth analysis. In Slovakia, it can be concluded that, although the links are weak or very weak, the most significant cooperations or memberships in spa or health clusters and cooperations or memberships in specific knowledge and innovation partnerships/innovation ecosystems/technological innovation clusters are of greatest importance regarding the effects of innovations. Conversely, the lowest, almost nonexistent, links are shown in the context of innovation from cooperation with secondary schools. The most significant perceived effect of cooperation on innovation is in the areas of sales as well as regional specialization, client satisfaction, and loyalty. Individually, the strongest link, a weak correlation, was shown between cooperation in spa or health clusters and sales.

In Spain, although all links are weak or very weak except one, it can be concluded that, in relation to the effects of innovation, the most important cooperation is with higher education institutions, followed by cooperation or membership in specific knowledge and innovation partnerships/innovation ecosystems/technological innovation clusters, as well as cooperation or membership in the tourism cluster or destination management organizations. In contrast, the lowest link in the context of innovation is found in cooperation or membership in spa or health clusters. The most significant perceived effect of cooperation on innovation is in regional economic development and the availability of external financial resources for business development. Overall, the strongest link, a moderate correlation, was observed between cooperation with higher education institutions and regional economic development (while in Slovakia, the links to innovation performance variables are very weak to negligible).

The results of examining the relationships between cooperation (Group1) and individual types of innovation clearly show positive links ranging from moderate to very weak. The correlation coefficient values are higher than when examining the links between cooperation and innovation performance, particularly in Slovakia, and slightly in Spain. This means that experts perceive the impact of cooperation on the implementation of innovations more significantly than on innovation performance itself.

The impact of cooperation is differently manifested according to experts in different types of innovations. For Slovakia, there is again very weak linkage to the greening of products and processes. This result may suggest that environmental innovations are not the primary focus of cooperative activities, or their implementation depends more on other factors. Especially in the context of the current and undeniably needed development towards sustainable growth, it can be assumed that there is a clear untapped potential for cooperation, especially in technological partnerships. The growing pressure for ecological production may also push spa enterprises to utilize partnerships in this direction, as is more clearly evident in Spain.

Currently, however, in Slovakia, there is a moderately strong link between the implementation of new management processes and a slightly stronger link between the introduction of new procedures and processes in service production and cooperation. In Spain, there is nearly no connection with new marketing processes. In Spain, cooperation is mainly used for the implementation and commercialization of new products, as well as for the introduction of new procedures and processes in service production.

A detailed view of the links between variables within both groups (Group1 and Group2) and interesting findings are in the core of the article. Overall, moderate correlations were proven in Slovakia and strong correlations in Spain between various forms of partnerships, as well as strong links between the effects of innovation in Slovakia and moderate correlations in Spain. In any case, these are mutually connected vessels, and it can be assumed that even if a certain form of cooperation did not show a significant correlation with the effects of innovation, it does not mean it cannot have a stronger indirect link.

The links between various forms of partnerships in Slovakia primarily show that businesses involved in innovation partnerships largely collaborate with higher education institutions. An interesting finding is also the moderately strong connection between secondary schools and higher education institutions with tourism clusters or destination management organizations. This finding (as well as others according to Figure 1) creates an assumption that knowledge and innovation transfer occurs

between various partnerships in Slovakia. This is also true for Spain, but in this country, much stronger links between partnerships are observed. Here, mutual links reach a strong correlation level (except for three links), and knowledge transfer mainly takes place between secondary schools and spa or health clusters, higher and secondary schools, and higher education institutions and innovation partnerships.

The studies suggest differences between Slovakia and Spain in the significance of different forms of partnerships in the context of innovation performance, as well as in the context of individual types of innovation. These differences may reflect regional specifics of the innovation environment in Slovakia and Spain and result from differing economic, cultural, political, and social conditions in both countries.

The higher links found between cooperation and innovation performance, as well as the stronger links between individual forms of partnerships in Spain, may imply a slightly higher level of the innovation ecosystem in this country, as well as a higher pressure for innovation and the utilization of cooperation potential in Spain. As stated in the literature review, Slovakia and Spain have different systems for funding spa treatments. A system based more heavily on direct financial flows from consumers to the service provider in spa tourism, exposed to a more competitive environment, will accelerate demand for innovations with greater intensity, managed through extensive cooperation. On the other hand, funding from health insurance sources may limit the flexibility of businesses in implementing innovations. Although spa tourism has a long tradition in Slovakia, it seems less flexible compared to Spain. Our findings confirm this assumption.

The original research presented here contributes to highlighting the potential of cooperation between spa enterprises and various partnerships supporting innovation performance. The individual findings may serve as a basis for policy setting at both the national and regional levels to build and support partnerships capable of supporting different types of innovations. However, the results may also indicate the opposite effect – the demand for innovations by spa enterprises may be one of the factors driving the interests and efforts of cooperative partnerships. The relationships between both phenomena are reciprocal; in any case, it has been proven that cooperation between spa enterprises in various interest partnerships belongs within the structure of the innovation ecosystem.

An interesting aspect is the possibility of comparing countries and identifying reasons for differences in statement/parameter values, as well as potential inspiration for problem-solving in countries/regions with a lower intensity of the problem. This particularly concerns regional tourism management but also the national level in relation to its competencies and the ability to influence regional development in terms of the examined parameters.

The results of the study open many new questions. Among them is the issue of identifying the factors influencing the degree of utilization of partnerships to support innovations in spa enterprises. A large space opens up for examining this issue in the context of several countries with similar as well as different systems for funding spa tourism.

Formatting of funding sources

This work was supported by by The Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic, which presents results from research project VEGA

1/0271/23 Sustainable renewal of spa tourism in the Slovak Republic in the context of the impacts of civilization crises.

References

1. Act No. 538/2005 The Act on Natural Healing Waters, Natural Healing Spas, Spas and Natural Mineral Waters and on the Amendment and Supplementation of Certain Acts. <https://www.slov-lex.sk/ezbierky/pravne-predpisy/SK/ZZ/2005/538/>
2. Act No. 577/2004 Act on the scope of health care paid on the basis of public health insurance and on payments for services related to the provision of health care. <https://www.zakonypreludi.sk/zz/2004-577>
3. Adams, R., Jeanrenaud, S., Bessant, J., Denyer, D., & Overy, P. (2016). Sustainability-oriented innovation: A systematic review. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 18(2), 180-205. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijmr.12068>
4. Anaya-Aguilar, R., Gemar, G., & Anaya-Aguilar, C. (2021). Factors associated with spa tourists' satisfaction. *Mathematics*, 9(4), 332. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math9040332>
5. Audretsch, D. B., Belitski, M., Caiazza, R., & Phan, P. (2023). Collaboration strategies and SME innovation performance. *Journal of Business Research*, 164, 114018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2023.114018>
6. Banevicius, S., & Narkiene, R. (2023). Regional Organizational Partnership In Health Tourism. *Management/Vadyba* (16487974), 39(2). <https://doi.org/10.38104/vadyba.2023.2.13>
7. Barros, C. L., & Sousa, B. B. (2022). Relationship Management in Spa Tourism: An Approach to Cross-Border Regions. In *Tourist Behavior* (pp. 1-22). Apple Academic Press.
8. Berzina, K. (2023). Cooperation Skill Evaluation In Spa And Wellness Sector For Sustainable Enterprise Development. *International Multidisciplinary Scientific GeoConference: SGEM*, 23(5.1), 345-351. <https://doi.org/10.5593/sgem2023/5.1/s21.44>
9. Blazevic, O. (2016). Health tourism and "smart specialisation". *UTMS Journal of Economics*, 7(1), 85-95. <https://hdl.handle.net/10419/174146>
10. Buhalis, D., & Foerste, M. (2015). SoCoMo marketing for travel and tourism: Empowering co-creation of value. *Journal of destination marketing & management*, 4(3), 151-161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2015.04.001>
11. Cantabene, C., & Grassi, I. (2024). Firm performance and R&D cooperation: what matters?. *Economics of Innovation and New Technology*, 33(1), 142-165. <http://hdl.handle.net/10.1080/10438599.2022.2145559>
12. Cassens, M., Hörmann, G., Tarnai, C., Stosiek, N., & Meyer, W. (2012). Trend Gesundheitstourismus. *Prävention und Gesundheitsförderung*, 1(7), 24-29. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11553-011-0313-2>
13. Costa, T., & Lima, M. J. (2018). Cooperation in tourism and regional development. *Tourism & management studies*, 14(4), 50-62. <https://doi.org/10.18089/tms.2018.14405>
14. Custódio Santos, M., Ferreira, A., Costa, C., & Santos, J. A. C. (2020). A model for the development of innovative tourism products: From service to

transformation. *Sustainability*, 12(11), 4362.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su12114362>

15. de Figueiredo, V. M. P., da Costa Guerra, R. J., & Gonçalves, E. C. C. (2021). Cooperation networks in tourism and hospitality: An analysis applied to health and wellness tourism product in Portugal. *Tourism Innovation in Spain and Portugal: New Trends and Developments*, 27-41. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80733-7_3
16. Gil de Arriba, C. (2000). La difusión social y espacial del modelo balneario: de la innovación médica al desarrollo de las prácticas de ocio. *Scripta Nova: revista electrónica de geografía y ciencias sociales*, 4. Retrieved from: <https://raco.cat/index.php/ScriptaNova/article/view/58791>.
17. Gómez Pérez, C. P., González Soutelo, S., Mourelle Mosqueira, M. L., & Legido Soto, J. L. (2019). Spa techniques and technologies: from the past to the present. *Sustainable Water Resources Management*, 5, 71-81. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40899-017-0136-1>
18. Gössling, S., Peeters, P., Hall, C. M., Ceron, J. P., Dubois, G., & Scott, D. (2012). Tourism and water use: Supply, demand, and security. An international review. *Tourism management*, 33(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2011.03.015>
19. Chen, X., & Ling, X. (2024). The influence mechanism of resource sharing on tourism industry innovation. *Heliyon*, 10(4). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e25855>
20. Ilic, B. S., Djuric, Z., Andjelic, S., Djukic, G. P., & Kruskovic, T. (2023). Research and Development of Regional Cooperation in Serbian Tourism: An Overview of the Health Tourism Sector. *Handbook of Research on Quality and Competitiveness in the Healthcare Services Sector*, 97-116. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-8103-5.ch006>
21. Instituto de Mayores y Servicios Sociales (IMSERSO). (n.d.). *Programa de turismo del Imserso*. Retrieved from: <https://imserso.es/espacio-mayores/envejecimiento-activo/programa-turismo-imserso>
22. Instituto Geológico y Minero de España (IGME). (2022a). *Aguas minerales de bebida envasada y balnearios en activo*. Retrieved from: <https://aguasmineralesytermales.igme.es/plantas-balnearios-en-funcionamiento>
23. Instituto Geológico y Minero de España (IGME). (2022b). *Estadísticas de balnearios en España*. Retrieved from: <https://aguasmineralesytermales.igme.es/ext/estadistica-ESP-balnearios.aspx>
24. Ismail, M., Bello-Pintado, A., & García-Marco, T. (2024). How many to be different? The role of number and the partner type on innovation performance. *Innovation*, 26(1), 145-168. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14479338.2022.2084545>
25. Kiron, D., Kruschwitz, N., Reeves, M., Haanaes, K., & Goh, E. (2012). The benefits of sustainability-driven innovation. *Own the Future: 50 Ways to Win from the Boston Consulting Group*, 119-123. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119204084.ch15>

26. Lebe, S. S. (2013). *European spa world: Chances for the project's sustainability through application of knowledge management*. In *Knowledge Sharing and Quality Assurance in Hospitality and Tourism* (pp. 137-146). Routledge. https://doi.org/10.1300/J162v07n01_08
27. Liu, M., Shan, Y., & Li, Y. (2023). Heterogeneous Partners, R&D cooperation and corporate innovation capability: Evidence from Chinese manufacturing firms. *Technology in Society*, 72, 102183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2022.102183>
28. Martín Megías, A. I. (2014). 25 años de Termalismo Social. Evolución de los establecimientos balnearios desde el punto de vista médico. *Boletín de la Sociedad Española de Hidrología Médica*, 29(1), 37-41. <https://doi.org/10.23853/bsehm.2017.0308>
29. McLeod, M., Vaughan, D. R., Edwards, J., & Moital, M. (2024). Knowledge sharing and innovation in open networks of tourism businesses. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 36(2), 438-456. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-03-2022-0326>
30. Mota, B., Rua, O. L., & Neira-Gómez, I. (2024). New advances in science mapping and performance analysis of the open innovation and tourism relationship. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 10(1), 100154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joitmc.2023.100154>
31. Moure, O. M., Peiró, P. S., & Lucas, M. O. (2013). El Programa de Termalismo Social del IMSERSO. Evolución y tendencias de futuro. *Aposta. Revista de Ciencias Sociales*, (59), 1-24. Retrieved from: <https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=495950255004>
32. Nagy, A. (2014). The orientation towards innovation of spa hotel management: the case of Romanian spa industry. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 124, 425-431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.02.504>
33. National Center For Health Information. (2022). Spa care in the Slovak Republic 2022. https://www.nczisk.sk/Statisticke_vystupy/Tematicke_statisticke_vystupy/KupeIna_starostlivost/Pages/default.aspx
34. National Center For Health Information. (2024). Spa care in the Slovak Republic 2023. https://data.nczisk.sk/statisticke_vystupy/Kupelna_starostlivost/Kupelna_starostlivost_SR_2023.pdf
35. Neuhofer, B., Buhalis, D., & Ladkin, A. (2015). Smart technologies for personalized experiences: a case study in the hospitality domain. *Electronic Markets*, 25, 243-254. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12525-015-0182-1>
36. Oborin, M. S., Osipov, V. S., & Skryl, T. V. (2019). Strategy for sustainable growth of SPA clusters based on the elements of network interaction. *Journal of Environmental Management and Tourism*, 9(8), 1768-1777. [https://doi.org/10.14505/jemt.v9.8\(32\).16](https://doi.org/10.14505/jemt.v9.8(32).16)
37. Perkumienė, D., Vienažindienė, M., & Švagždienė, B. (2019). Cooperation perspectives in sustainable medical tourism: The case of Lithuania. *Sustainability*, 11(13), 3584. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11133584>
38. Pikkemaat, B., & Weiermair, K. (2007). Innovation through cooperation in destinations: first results of an empirical study in Austria. *Anatolia*, 18(1), 67-83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13032917.2007.9687036>

39. Pinos Navarrete, A., & Shaw, G. (2021). Spa tourism opportunities as strategic sector in aiding recovery from Covid-19: The Spanish model. *Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 21(2), 245-250. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1467358420970626>
40. Pinos Navarrete, A., Shaw, G., & Martos, J. C. M. (2020). Towards wellness? A case study of the profile of tourists visiting a Southern Spanish Spa. *International Journal of Spa and Wellness*, 3(1), 40-55. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24721735.2020.1857208>
41. Prokop, V., Kotková Stříteská, M., & Stejskal, J. (2021). Fostering Czech firms' innovation performance through efficient cooperation. *Oeconomia Copernicana*, 12(3), 671–700. <https://doi.org/10.24136/oc.2021.022>
42. Radicic, D., & Alkaraan, F. (2024). Relative effectiveness of open innovation strategies in single and complex SME innovators. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 36(9), 2113-2126. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537325.2022.2130042>
43. R Core Team. (2024). A language and environment for statistical computing. Retrieved from: <http://www.R-project.org/>
44. Rodek, N., Máhr, T., & Birkner, Z. (2020). Innovation in the Service Sector: A Possible Recipe for Success for the Spa Towns of Central Europe. *ENTRENOVA-ENTerprise REsearch InNOVation*, 6(1), 504-511. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/250977>
45. Rodriguez Sanchez, I., Williams, A. M., & García Andreu, H. (2020). Customer resistance to tourism innovations: entrepreneurs' understanding and management strategies. *Journal of Travel Research*, 59(3), 450-464. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287519843188>
46. Sánchez Rodríguez, E. (2022). Análisis de la reputación online del turismo de balnearios en España: acercamiento a su visibilidad web en tiempos de Covid-19. *Gran tour, Revista de investigaciones turísticas*, (24). Retrieved from: <https://www.eutm.es/grantour/index.php/grantour/article/view/249>
47. Santoro, G., Bresciani, S., & Papa, A. (2020). Collaborative modes with cultural and creative industries and innovation performance: the moderating role of heterogeneous sources of knowledge and absorptive capacity. *Technovation*, 92, 102040. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2018.06.003>
48. Scott, D., Hall, C. M., & Gössling, S. (2019). Global tourism vulnerability to climate change. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 77, 49-61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2019.05.007>
49. Semenova, Z. A., Chistobaev, A. I., & Grudtcyn, N. A. (2020). Management of the public-private partnership in health tourism. *Revista Espacios*, 41(15). <https://www.revistaespacios.com/a20v41n15/a20v41n15p14.pdf>
50. Smith, M., & Puczkó, L. (2014). *Health, tourism and hospitality: Spas, wellness and medical travel*. Routledge
51. Statistical Office of The Slovak Republic. (2023). *Public database DATAcube*. https://datacube.statistics.sk/#!/view/sk/VBD_SLOVSTAT/zd2007rs/v_zd2007rs_00_00_00_sk

52. Statistical Office of The Slovak Republic. (2024). *Spa Tourism in Slovakia for 2023*. <https://slovakiatravel.org/2024/06/24/kupelny-cestovny-ruch-na-slovensku-v-roku-2023/>
53. Szromek, A. R. (2021). The sustainable business model of spa tourism enterprise—results of research carried out in Poland. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 7(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc7010073>
54. Szromek, A. R., & Polok, G. (2022). A business model for spa tourism enterprises: transformation in a period of sustainable change and humanitarian crisis. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 8(2), 72. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc8020072>
55. Szymanska, E., & Lech, J. (2017). Modern tendencies in spa tourism: innovations. *Economic and Social Development: Book of Proceedings*, 67-75.
56. Szymańska, E., Rutkowski, A., & Panfiluk, E. (2016). The open innovation process in SPA & wellness tourism. *European Journal of Service Management*, 19, 59-66. <https://doi.org/10.18276/ejism.2016.19-08>
57. Šoltés, E. (2019). *Regression and correlation analysis with applications in SAS software*. Letra Edu
58. Temel, S., Mention, A. L., & Yurtseven, A. E. (2023). Cooperation for innovation: more is not necessarily merrier. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 26(2), 446-474. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-10-2020-0392>
59. Trip, D. T., Simut, R., & Badulescu, D. (2023). Do size and ownership determine the willingness for sustainable innovations in Spa and health tourism? A case study on Baile Felix spa resort, Romania. *Sustainability*, 15(19), 14501. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151914501>
60. Tseng, F. C., Huang, M. H., & Chen, D. Z. (2020). Factors of university–industry collaboration affecting university innovation performance. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 45, 560-577. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-018-9656-6>
61. Valderrama, E. L., & Polanco, J. A. (2024). Understanding how collaborative governance mediates rural tourism and sustainable territory development: a systematic literature review. *Tourism Recreation Research*, 49(4), 888-904. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508281.2022.2072653>
62. Valeriani, F., Margarucci, L. M., & Romano Spica, V. (2018). Recreational use of spa thermal waters: criticisms and perspectives for innovative treatments. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(12), 2675 <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15122675>
63. Wang, C., & Hu, Q. (2020). Knowledge sharing in supply chain networks: Effects of collaborative innovation activities and capability on innovation performance. *Technovation*, 94, 102010. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2017.12.002>
64. Wang, F., Su, Q., & Zhang, Z. (2024). The influence of collaborative innovation network characteristics on firm innovation performance from the perspective of innovation ecosystem. *Kybernetes*, 53(4), 1281-1305. <https://doi.org/10.1108/K-04-2022-0553>
65. Wilke, E. P., Costa, B. K., Freire, O. B. D. L., & Ferreira, M. P. (2019). Interorganizational cooperation in tourist destination: Building performance in the hotel industry. *Tourism Management*, 72, 340-351. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2018.12.015>

66. Wu, A. (2020). Improving tourism innovation performance: linking perspectives of asset specificity, intellectual capital, and absorptive capacity. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 44(6), 908-930. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1096348020927453>
67. Wu, Y., Gu, F., Ji, Y., Guo, J., & Fan, Y. (2020). Technological capability, eco-innovation performance, and cooperative R&D strategy in new energy vehicle industry: Evidence from listed companies in China. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 261, 121157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121157>
68. Xiang, Z., Du, Q., Ma, Y., & Fan, W. (2017). A comparative analysis of major online review platforms: Implications for social media analytics in hospitality and tourism. *Tourism Management*, 58, 51-65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2016.10.001>
69. Xu, R., Wu, J., Gu, J., & Raza-Ullah, T. (2023). How inter-firm cooperation and conflicts in industrial clusters influence new product development performance? The role of firm innovation capability. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 111, 229-241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2023.04.009>
70. Zhang, S., Chen, C., & Deng, C. (2024). University-industry collaboration portfolio concentration and focal firms' innovation performance: evidence from China. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 36(5), 975-988. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537325.2022.2067038>